

INNOVATIVE MANAGEMENT AND ORGANIZATIONAL INITIATIVES IN PROMOTING PROFESSIONAL COLLABORATION AND SCHOOL PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

To have great leaders who see how to establish innovative management, the structure of leader training should be thought of. Being an administration that is made sure about by specific establishments, instruction cannot be detached from the individuals who convey this management from their abilities and assurance. Henceforth, the organization initiatives and innovation in education converse to enter components in the consummation of a particular instructive act. This study focused on the innovative management and organizational initiatives in promoting professional collaboration and school performance. This study utilized a descriptive and correlational type of research. The respondents of this study were eighty seven (87) public elementary teachers who are currently employed at Lucena North District, Division of Lucena City. The researcher utilized a self-devised questionnaire in gathering the necessary data of the study derived from the different related literature and studies. The data gathered in innovative management practices as to continuous improvement, implementation of practice, structure, techniques, and management process, practiced these to a great extent. In organizational initiatives as described by the response in terms of value creation, lean start up, organization culture, and core interest, these were observed to a great extent. Thus, the data gathered indicated in professional collaboration as to learning atmosphere, staff engagement, staff development, openness, and partnerships were manifested to a great extent. Hence, the school performance as described in the learner achievement, internal efficiency, and teacher performance revealed as excellent. Analysis of the data gathered revealed that innovative management practices have positive significant relationship to professional collaboration and school performance as well as organizational initiatives practices have positive significant relationship to professional collaboration and school performance. After numerous statistical treatments, we can draw that there is a high correlation between innovative management and organizational initiatives in promoting professional collaboration and school performance. The study indicates that the utilization of innovative management and organizational initiatives in promoting professional collaboration and school performance encourages a positive significant increase in the progress of the educational system.

Keywords: innovative management, organizational initiatives, professional collaboration, school performance